

Study of Sodium Aluminate in Conjunction with Alum for Coagulation of Red Water of the Ganges

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Red water in the Ganges river possesses a problem in coagulation, requiring excessive alum. The resistance to coagulation is possibly due to fineness of the colloidal particle. The application of sodium aluminate along with basic alum is found to be a better combination for efficient coagulation possibly due to enhanced hydrolysis of alum in presence of sodium aluminate and increased sorption of hydrolysed alum by clay particles.

CLAY fraction collected from the Ganges water (near Palta Water Works) in monsoon period differs from that collected in the premonsoon period with respect to its exchangeable bases, textural constituents and also in relation to contents of SiO_2 , R_2O_3 , MgO , K_2O and structurally bonded water. It is reported that the monsoon clay is predominantly illitic in nature while the premonsoon one is kaolinitic¹.

Water in the Ganges at the very outset of the monsoonal rain assumes red colour and is very difficult to coagulate economically and needs excessive alum. High dosage of alum depresses the pH which introduces a number of problems i.e., pipe line corrosion, plankton mortality etc. The troubles involved in red water clarification by alum may be controlled by conventional sodium aluminate.²

The present purpose is to study the possibility of using aluminate in clarification of red water from the Ganges. Sodium aluminate is usually not accepted as a primary coagulant for clarification of large municipal supplies considering its costs with respect to acid coagulants². However, there is possibility of its use as an adjunct particularly in case of red water clarification. An attempt has been made to justify the applicability of sodium aluminate along with alum in clarification of troublesome red water from the Ganges.

Material and Methods

River water samples were collected from a fixed depth of the basin. Throughout the red water period (i.e., early monsoon from 2nd week of June to last week of July of every year) and some other representative samples were also collected for comparison before and after the period. Turbidity of all these samples were measured with the aid of Jackson's candle turbidimeter. The other relevant physico-chemical characteristics of the sample were deter-

mined by the standard procedure³. The zeta-potential, ionic mobility and specific conductance were ascertained by electrophoretic mobility measurements⁴.

To determine the alum dosages for limiting coagulation (below 5 units in SiO_2 scale as prescribed by ICMR and WHO) the laboratory study consisted of a series of Jar Tests where the variables were examined to standardise the procedure⁵. To attain reproducibility in each case, floc size, time of floc formation, settling characteristics⁴ and temperature of the system were recorded. Bacterial population both in alum treated and alum+aluminate treated water were determined by determining presumptive coliform count⁶. Algal enumeration was done as usual⁷.

Results and Discussion

For the sake of characterization, premonsoon water samples collected under identical conditions were compared with those of red water samples (Table 1).

Table 2 refers to coagulation of river water with variable dosages of alum and sodium aluminate. To study the possibility of sodium aluminate as an adjunct to coagulation along with the prime coagulant alum, a series of parallel static methods (not provided with a mechanical stirrer after initial thorough dispersion of addendas) as trial runs were performed simultaneously with varied ratios of basic alum and sodium aluminate to assess the effective dosages (between alum and aluminate) and it was concluded from such preliminary observations that the effective ratio of alum and aluminate should be 20 : 1 (Al_2O_3 content in alum 17.5%, aluminate 50%). Further increase in the dosage of adjunct possibly effects charge reversals of flocs^{4,8} (from positive to

TABLE 1—COMPARATIVE STUDY OF RED WATER WITH ORDINARY WATER

	Red Water (Monsoon)		Ordinary Water Premonsoon	
	Range	Mean	Range	Mean
pH	7.80 to 7.90	7.80	7.90 to 8.10W	8.00
Turbidity (in SiO ₂ Scale) p.p.m.	600 to 1200	1000	100 to 2000	1200
Salinity (in Cl Scale) „	10 to 15	12	10 to 1200	500
Alkalinity (in CaCO ₃ Scale) „	75 to 125	85	75 to 300	250
Total Dissolved Solids „	100 to 150	120	50 to 1000	650
Total hardness (in CaCO ₃ Scale) „	80 to 200	150	50 to 500	400
Permanent hardness („) „	0 to 2	1	5 to 200	25
Total Iron (Fe ⁺⁺ + Fe ⁺⁺⁺) „	6.00 to 8.00	7.50	1.20 to 5.00	4.25
Soluble Iron (Fe ⁺⁺) „	1.00 to 3.50	2.75	0.50 to 2.00	1.30
Dissolved Oxygen „	4.00 to 4.50	4.20	4.30 to 6.00	5.50
Oxygen Consumed „	4.00 to 4.50	4.00	2.00 to 5.00	2.50
Ionic Mobility cm ² /volt ⁻¹ sec ⁻¹	1.2 × 10 ⁻⁴ to 1.3 × 10 ⁻⁴	1.275 × 10 ⁻⁴	1.4 × 10 ⁻⁴ to 1.65 × 10 ⁻⁴	1.435 × 10 ⁻⁴
Zetapotential	27.50 to 28.00	27.55	28.30 to 29.50	23.00
Specific Conductance mho/cm	2.235 × 10 ⁻⁴ to 2.465 × 10 ⁻⁴	2.355 × 10 ⁻⁴	2.880 × 10 ⁻⁴ to 2.910 × 10 ⁻⁴	2.9 × 10 ⁻⁴
Bacterial Count in MPN (most probable number)	5,000 to 35,000	25,000	6,000 to 38,000	15,000

TABLE 2—A TYPICAL STUDY OF COAGULATION OF RIVER WATER (RED WATER) WITH ALUM ALONE AND TOGETHER WITH SODIUM ALUMINATE

Specification of River Water : Turbidity (in SiO₂ scale) : 1000 ppm; Salinity (in Cl scale) : 15 ppm; Alkalinity (in CaCO₃ scale) : 84 ppm; pH : 7.90

Available Al ₂ O ₃ in alum used	Alum in ppm (fixed)	Sodium aluminate in ppm (variable)	Time of flocculation in minutes	Remark in case of alum + aluminate treatment	Only alum treatment dose in ppm	Remark in case of only alum treatment	Sodium aluminate in ppm (fixed)	Alum in ppm (variable)	Time of flocculation in minutes	Remark in case of alum + aluminate treatment
17.60%	39.20	1.65	10	(c)	53.50	(e)	1.40	19.00	(x)	(a)
		2.10	7	(d)				22.00	12	(b)
		2.80	6	(f)				25.00	10	(b)
		3.05	4	(g)				28.00	7	(b)
14.60%	39.20	1.65	15	(b)			1.40	19.00	(x)	(a)
		2.10	12	(c)				22.00	(x)	(a)
		2.80	12	(c)				25.00	(x)	(a)
		3.05	10	(d)				28.00	15	(b)

Significance of the letters (a) to (g) and (x) : (a) Poor floc and no settlement.
 (b) Very poor floc with poor settlement.
 (c) Compact coarse flock but delayed settlement.
 (d) Compact coarse flock with quick settlement.
 (e) Fair floc with moderate settlement.
 (f) Fair floc with quick settlement.
 (g) Large well formed flock with immediate settlement.
 (x) Means no flocculation, hence inapplicable.

Average of 25 samples were taken for each turbidity range and coagulant dosage fixation.

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TABLE 3—STATIC METHOD TO FIND OUT THE EFFECTIVE RATIO BETWEEN ALUM AND ALUMINATE

Turbidity in units	Nature of treatments		Turbidity at different intervals				Floc characteristics at different intervals			
	Alum in ppm	Aluminate in ppm	0 hr.	1 hr.	6 hrs.	24 hrs.	0 hr.	1 hr.	5 hrs.	24 hrs.
300	0.30	0.03	250	210	130	30	(x)	(a)	(a)	(b)
	0.40	0.04	200	140	75	70	(x)	(a)	(b)	(c)
	0.50	0.05	200	140	65	15	(a)	(b)	(c)	(f)
180	0.20	0.02	180	160	70	30	(x)	(a)	(b)	(c)
	0.30	0.02	120	75	40	15	(a)	(b)	(c)	(d)
	0.40	0.02	100	65	35	15	(a)	(b)	(c)	(f)
900	2.00	0.10	800	600	330	120	(x)	(a)	(a)	(b)
	2.20	0.12	720	210	95	25	(a)	(a)	(c)	(d)
	2.40	0.12	720	175	75	15	(a)	(c)	(d)	(f)
900	0.60	0.06	900	320	165	50	(x)	(x)	(x)	(a)
	0.70	0.07	900	200	100	30	(x)	(x)	(x)	(a)
	0.80	0.08	900	180	80	20	(x)	(a)	(b)	(c)
600	0.80	0.06	350	170	35	20	(b)	(c)	(e)	(f)
	0.60	0.06	450	250	200	75	(a)	(b)	(d)	(e)
	0.80	0.08	200	130	50	15	(c)	(c)	(d)	(f)
1800	2.00	0.10	1500	190	65	15	(a)	(b)	(c)	(d)
	1.80	0.09	1600	200	75	15	(a)	(b)	(b)	(f)
	1.60	0.08	1700	550	110	25	(a)	(a)	(b)	(d)
	2.00	0.14	1450	800	320	70	(a)	(b)	(c)	(f)
1200	1.60	0.08	1000	240	85	20	(a)	(b)	(d)	(f)
	1.40	0.07	800	290	100	25	(a)	(b)	(c)	(f)
	1.20	0.06	850	600	140	35	(a)	(b)	(d)	(f)
	1.60	0.10	900	800	260	65	(a)	(b)	(d)	(f)
1600	3.00	0.15	1200	260	75	15	(b)	(d)	(e)	(f)
	2.80	0.14	1350	290	95	15	(a)	(c)	(d)	(e)
	3.00	0.20	1200	550	180	35	(b)	(d)	(f)	(f)
	2.80	0.20	1300	800	240	65	(a)	(c)	(d)	(f)

Significance of the letters (a) to (f) & (x) : (a) Poor floc.
 (b) Fair floc.
 (c) Fairly good floc.
 (d) Uniformly loose floc.
 (e) Uniformly fine floc.
 (f) Almost complete settlement.
 (x) No floc at all.

0 hr. means just after the time of alum and sodium aluminate addition.
 An average of 25 samples were taken for each turbidity and coagulant dosage fixation.

negative) and clarification was, consequently inhibited when adjunct dosage was lower than the optimum. There is, however, an apparent anomaly in 8th and 9th columns in Table 2 which is due to the fact that comparative study of these two columns with 2nd and 3rd columns of the same table clearly reveal the lower Al_2O_3 present in the former case obviating poor flocculation, although the ratio is 20 : 1. The optimum floc formation can thus be effected only by increased basal aluminate doze together with proportionate rise in alum also so that the effective Al_2O_3 content becomes nearly equal in both the cases. For that particular sample, most suitable combined dosage as used was 1.92 ppm aluminate and 38.40 ppm basic alum to have maximum economy and floc formation was noted within 6 mins only. The dosage, e.g., 1.40 in 8th column of Table 2 were suggested empirically near to optimum.

The desired floc formation was badly hindered due to lessened hydrolysis of alum as shown in Table 2. It can be inferred from Table 3 that within the range

of turbidity of 180 to 1800 ppm of Ganges water, particularly, in Red water period, the optimum ratio between aluminate and alum as 1 : 20. gave a satisfactory result. Increased dosage of aluminate up to some limit may still yield better result with a favoured hydrolysis of alum.

Resistance to coagulation in case of red clay (i.e., clay present in red water) was earlier presumed to be either due to charge reversal of clay myceli^{4,8} originated from Fe^{3+}/Al^{3+} adsorption from lateritic wash or due to low charge density in the dispersing medium because of low salinity and alkalinity during this period (Table 1). Electrokinetic coagulation of red clay was thus performed by the anionic counterpart of basic alum i.e., by sulphate which result in a depression of pH. A typical red water sample of turbidity 1062 units and initial pH 8.44 on treatment with 84 ppm of alum for optimal coagulation showed the ultimate pH 6.95. However, the electrophoretic study, showed a different picture. The zetapotential measurements showed no remarkable difference

between the clay samples of two periods (i.e., monsoon and premonsoon as shown in Table 1). The hindrance to coagulation cannot, therefore, be explained on the basis of reversed charge on the red clay, but may be due to size. The illitic (hydrous mica) clay content is higher and montmorillonitic clay content is lower in the red water¹. The high dosage of alum requirement thus can be accounted on the ground of particle size of clay⁴.

The partial substitution of coagulant e.g., alum with sodium aluminate, causes partial removal of magnesium hardness² and disinfection up to the limit of 80 to 90% viz., a typical red water sample of turbidity 800 ppm, Mg^{++} content (in terms of $CaCO_3$): 32 ppm and MPN: 45,000 per 100 ml on treatment with 30.8 ppm of alum and 1.54 ppm of sodium aluminate showed ultimately turbidity 2 ppm with Mg^{++} content (in terms of $CaCO_3$) 20 ppm and MPN 40 per 100 ml. It was also noted from 'culturing technique' that the colour of the red water was possibly neither of algal nor bacterial origin⁷, but mainly due to lateritic wash of the early monsoon.

As an explanation to lower consumption of alum in presence of aluminate it may be stated¹⁰ that after initial charge neutralisation of finer clay in red water with Al^{3+} ion, the resultant Al (clay)₃ floc readily undergo flocculation due to sorption of $Al(OH)_3$ derived out of the enhanced hydrolysis of residual alum (not used up during the primary charge neutralisation phase through ion-exchange) in presence of sodium aluminate. The flocculation is thus improved.

In actual practice alum is cheaper than sodium aluminate. The high cost of sodium aluminate is,

however, compensated by the lowered consumption of prime coagulant i.e., basic alum, besides the fact that it helps coagulation of red water in the Ganges that means it ultimately reduces the cost of water treatment for municipal supply without hampering any condition of potability.

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